

Overview of the database resource

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The EBP-Nor database (<https://ebp-nor.sfb.uit.no>) is a relational database consisting of 5 linked tables (Fig.1). In simple terms, each table can be thought of as a separate spreadsheet with dedicated attribute columns for the type of record to populate it (species, isolates, specimens, sequencing runs, assembled genomes).

The relational structure is based on the project necessity for information on distinct levels. The EBP-Nor hierarchy follows as Fig.1:

1. Species
2. Isolate (shared top-level hierarchy to allow metagenomic species detection)
3. Specimen (tissue)
4. Sequencing
5. Assembly

Definitions

- A *record* is a row of data in a database table, comparable to a row in a spreadsheet.
- The *species* is the top-level record defining the possible connections to records in other databases below.
- In the EBP-Nor database an *isolate* record is a separate and unique individual of a given species.
 - Alternatively, the result of a metagenomic survey discovering a new species.
- Whereas a *specimen* is defined as the sub-sample (e.g., organ, tissue, body part, whole body) of an isolate.
 - Alternatively, the specimen can also be a combination of two isolates; for example, mixing of male and female isolates intended for joint DNA/RNA sequencing.
- One or multiple *sequencing runs* can be made from a single specimen.
- The final *assembly* can be a construct of one to multiple sequencing runs.

Since the databases can be linked it provides a flexible means of maintaining records across it.

Each database has an attribute for naming the record, here with examples:

Scientific name	Rangifer tarandus (mRanTar)
Isolate name	mRanTar1
Specimen name	mRanTar1_muscle
Sequencing/experiment alias name	ebp-nor_exp_mrantar1_muscle
Run alias name	ebp-nor_run_mrantar1_muscle

Assembly name	ebp-nor_asm_mrantar1_muscle
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The EBP-Nor database web page

The homepage (<https://ebp-nor.sfb.uit.no>) contain links to the five databases of EBP-Nor through its menu and shows a map of all isolates recorded in the database. Tips: Use the zoom function in your web-browser (Crome etc.) to improve how the database tables are shown. The homepage map will only show published isolates (having coordinates) for site visitors without an account. Records in the draft/working version will be shown on the map for users with account privileges as owner or writer. There are four membership roles, independent for each of the 5 databases, where the higher tier always includes the privileges of the lower:

1. Visitor / Pending request
 - Can only browse published data and download single records.
2. Reader
 - Can download all published data.
3. Writer
 - Access to editing draft entries (add, remove, modify – including TSV file operations).
4. Owner
 - Can edit database configuration and membership.

Applying for membership/ request database user role

Navigate to the database you like to work with and use the log in button (Fig. 2) to first register/log in to Life Science Login. Afterwards you can apply for a writer role in the database if you intend to work and edit entries. Follow the same progress for the other databases if these are relevant for you to edit. You might contact one of the database owners once you have applied for a role since there are no current automatic notifications sent.

Database owners:

- terje.klemetsen@uit.no
- nils-peder.willassen@uit.no
- igor.molchanov@uit.no

CBF functionalities as writer

Navigation. The Contextual biodata framework (CBF) is the system which provides all functionalities in the databases and the links connecting them as a relational database. Its foundation is the MongoDB database. Fig. 3 below shows the basic functions for navigating the databases. Clicking on a listed record brings up all the attributes related to it.

EBP-Nor

Home Databases How to

EARTH BIOGENOME PROJECT

Species

1.0

Text search...

Log out

Showing records 1 to 25 out of 130

Scientific name	Common name (nor.)	Family	Isolate name(s)	Isolate	Specimen name(s)	Specimen	Sequencing name(s)	Sequencing	Assembly name	Assembly
Alices alces (000000130)	- Elg - Europeisk elg	Cervidae	EBPN_ON_0123_01	000000008	- Alices_alces01 - Alices_lang01 - Alices_alces02	- 000000004 - 000000008 - 000000007	-	000000001	-	000000001
Caligus elongatus (000000129)	Skottelus	Caligidae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Conium maculatum (000000128)	Giffljeks	Apiaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Usnea longissima (000000127)	Huldrestrey	Parmeliaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Page size 25

Fig. 3 - Main website functionalities. A) Table configuration, data download, TSV upload. B) The current version of the database and drop-down choices for which version to show. If logged in as writer the draft will be shown in italic. C) Quick text search (type in the field and hit enter), advanced text search (click the magnifier button). D) Switch between table view, graph view and configuration (owner privileges required). E) Log in/out, register, and apply for database role. F) Navigation between databases

Note 1. If you are a writer/owner, you will see the draft version of the database if logged in. Given that version 1.0 is published for all visitors to see, you as a writer will see version 1.1 in italic (Fig. 3B) and can easily switch to view v1.0.

Note 2. If changes are made to any attribute of any record in draft version 1.1 the CBF will publish this automatically at 2 AM in the night. Afterwards, visitors will see version 1.1 and you as a writer/owner will see version 1.2. If needed, a version can be deprecated to make it unavailable for visitors.

Quick search and adding filters

In the search box, shown in Fig. 3, you may type in a search word and hit enter to perform a quick search. Clicking on the magnifier button-icon brings up the filtering functions. Simple to use but can look daunting due to the script showing up.

A filter consists of statements. A statement holds the attribute to search within, the search function to use, and what to search for. See screenshot below for a simple example of filtering the Scientific name attribute only.

1. Upper: The attribute to apply the filter. Example: Scientific name
2. Middle: The type of filter (equals, regex, before and after (for date fields), ontologies/compact IRI, CV (Controlled Vocabulary) and so forth.
3. Lower: Input and/or secondary options for the filter type. E.g., case sensitive, what ontology, what CV.

Filters

AND

New filter

Add statement

Scientific name

equals

Alices alces

Add

? Clear all Apply

An uncomplicated guide to make a filter showing the 2 genera Saxifraga and Labrus:

Click on the magnifier button in the species database.

Under add statement chose the following dropdowns from the top: Scientific name, matches (regex), Case insensitive, type in "Saxifraga*," click Add. Now only change the last input by removing "Saxifraga*" and type in

“Labrus*” instead, click Add again. Your filter should look like the screenshot below. Click Apply to filter the table accordingly.

Insensitive search does not consider caps. And in regex the asterisk () means that anything proceeding does not count and will show up after applying the filter.*

The screenshot shows a 'Filters' panel with a list of filter rules. One rule is highlighted with a blue box:

```

AND
  OR {"$or": [{"attrs.tax:sci_name.obj.val": {"$regex": "/Saxifraga*"}}, {"attrs.tax:sci_name.obj.iri": {"$regex": "/Saxifraga*"}}]}
  OR {"$or": [{"attrs.tax:sci_name.obj.val": {"$regex": "/Labrus*"}}, {"attrs.tax:sci_name.obj.iri": {"$regex": "/Labrus*"}}]}
  
```

To the right is an 'Add statement' form with the following fields:

- Scientific name (dropdown)
- matches (regex) (dropdown)
- Case insensitive (dropdown)
- Labrus* (text input)

Buttons include 'New filter', 'Add', '?', 'Clear all', and 'Apply'.

Result:

The screenshot shows a data table with 145 total records, displaying records 1 to 6. The table has the following columns:

Scientific name	Synonym name	Family	Sampling status	Isolate name(s)	Isolate	Specimen name(s)	Specimen	Sequencing name(s)	Sequencing	Assembly name	Assembly
Labrus bergylta (000000362)	-	Labridae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Saxifraga cotyledon (000000384)	-	Saxifragaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Saxifraga osloensis (000000291)	-	Saxifragaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Saxifraga adscendens (000000432)	-	Saxifragaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Saxifraga tridactylites (000000418)	-	Saxifragaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Saxifraga hyperborea (000000424)	-	Saxifragaceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Adding records

The CBF enables you to add a record on the fly using the (+) *Add data > New record* (Fig. 4). Doing so will bring up the attributes schema ready to be filled. **Note!** *Only after saving the entry can it be linked with other databases (more on linking entries later).*

An alternative way to add new entries is through the preparation and uploading of a tab separated (tsv) file (Fig. 4 and 5). Upload using the create function requires the use of minimum 1 attribute held by the database. The “id” attribute must be omitted as this is managed automatically by CBF. The tsv column names must use the attributes associated with the given database and the attribute SHORT NAME as listed in the EBP-Nor manifest. An example can be seen in the table screenshot below. For simplicity, one can download a template tsv (Fig. 4, second button from top) with all assigned attribute names for the given database.

The Sampling schema has output sheets for isolate and specimen data. If the sheet is filled in excel it can easily be uploaded as tsv files to make new records with the accompanying metadata.

Fig. 4 - Adding data. New record and TSV file upload.

New edit

1. Prepare data
 Addition, update and deletion of entries is done by submitting a [TSV file](#), which you can build from the following ways:
 - Download an [empty spreadsheet](#) and fill it up with your data.
 - Download the [minified dataset](#) (filter is applied) and edit it as needed.
 We recommend using [OpenRefine](#) if your input file contains hundreds of entries or more.
2. Upload data (.tsv or .tsv.gz)

Choose file No file chosen

Create/Overwrite ⓘ

Update existing ⓘ

[Upload \(create\)](#)

Fig. 5 - Uploading a TSV to **create** new records or upload to **overwrite/update** existing records.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	tax:sci_name	dblink:species	sam:isolate	pbb:sam_name	pbb:pre_tissue	pbb:part_size
2	Alaria esculenta	ebpnr.species:000000013	EBPN_ON_0123_01	AlaEsc_leg01	Leg	Medium
3	Alaria esculenta	ebpnr.species:000000013	EBPN_ON_0123_01	AlaEsc_heart01	Heart	Small
4	Alaria esculenta	ebpnr.species:000000013	EBPN_ON_0123_01	AlaEsc_leg02	Leg	Medium
5	Alaria esculenta	ebpnr.species:000000013	EBPN_ON_0123_01	AlaEsc_lung01	Lung	Small
6	Alaria esculenta	ebpnr.species:000000013	EBPN_ON_0123_01	AlaEsc_blood01	Blood	Very small
7	Trichaptum laricinum	ebpnr.species:000000047	EBPN_ON_0123_02	TriLar_mycelium01	Mycelium	Very small
8	Trichaptum laricinum	ebpnr.species:000000047	EBPN_ON_0123_02	TriLar_bodywall01	Bodywall	Small
9	Parnassius mnemosyne	ebpnr.species:000000035	EBPN_KN_0123_01	ParMne_abdomen01	Abdomen	Small
10	Parnassius mnemosyne	ebpnr.species:000000035	EBPN_KN_0123_01	ParMne_wing01	Wing	Small

Editing in a spreadsheet. You might want to download the whole database table as tsv for editing multiple records in one go in programs like excel. After finishing your changes in excel, you can export as tsv and upload this to the database using the “Update existing” function. This will overwrite/update the records you upload. Say that you want to modify 20 records, you can download the whole database and remove all but the 20 records you want to work with. The “id” column must remain in the tsv for this to work, the other columns are optional. If you remove the “id” column the CBF believes these are new entries instead. Therefore the “id” column must be present when modifying a tsv, while it must be excluded when adding multiple new entries.

Editing a record

Clicking on any listed record in the database brings up the record view (Fig. 7). It is worth noting that all attributes can be configured by a member with owner privileges (Change attribute name, tooltip, tab structure, arrangement of attributes, field type, etc.). Anyone with writer permission can edit a record by entering edit mode (Fig. 7A middle button).

You are watching a draft version of this record.

EBPN_ON_0123_02 (000000010) 10 **B.**

Isolate | Time and location | Natural history specimen | Collector | Taxonomy | Related records | Record metadata

A. Isolate

C.

① Isolate name	EBPN_ON_0123_02
① Scientific name	Trichaptum laricinum
① Sampling status	Collected
① Lifestage	Spore bearing structure
① Relationship	Not applicable
① Sex	Not provided
① Symbiont	Not applicable
① Risk of mixed samples	Yes
① Environment material	Not applicable
① Environment sample name	EBPN_ON_0123_02
① BioSample accession	-
① Other information	-

[Close](#)

Fig. 7 - Record view of an example entry in the Isolate database. A) Menu for downloading the entry metadata, enter edit mode, delete the entry. B) The header is a combination of the isolate name and the id attribute. C) Each attribute has a tooltip for further description.

Opening a record and you will have access to the Edit button if you are logged in with writer privileges.

Field types

In edit mode the simplest field types are free text and are recognized by not having any dropdown choices (controlled vocabulary), nor ontology associated. However, free text fields can be mandatory as shown below, preventing the record from being saved if not filled.

⚠ Isolate name ⓪

This field is compulsory.

Controlled vocabularies, shown below, are pre-defined choices and are recognized by a small down-arrow on the field's right-hand side.

① Specimen id mix risk ⓪

✓ -
 No
 Not applicable
 Yes

[Cancel](#) [Save](#)

Date fields follow the ISO8601 format and accept year, month, date in truncated variants.

① Sampling date YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM or YYYY ⓪

The *environment material* and *habitat* attributes are examples where ontology use is supported. Ontologies are recognized by 2 fields, a drop-down menu, and an input field. By selecting the “-” no ontology will be used, and the input field works as a free text field. By selecting the “envo” you can choose to use the Environment Ontology (ENVO) and input identifiers representing a class term. E.g., to link the envo class “[temperate forest](#)” you must input

the corresponding identifier “01001805” and save the record. Tips: Use [Ontobee](#) or other envO ontology search tools to find classes and their identifiers. This will make CBF collect the ontology class information and make a link to ebi.ac.uk/ols for the given term as well as displaying a tooltip containing the term definition.

The screenshot shows two rows of the CBF form. The first row has 'Risk of mixed samples' set to 'No'. The second row has 'Environment material' set to 'envo'. The third row shows 'Environment material' with 'envo' selected in the dropdown and '01001805' entered in the text field.

Result:

The screenshot shows the result of the form. The 'Environment material' field is set to 'Temperate forest'. A tooltip is displayed over the field, showing the identifier 'envo:01001805', the term 'No', and the description: 'Description: A forest ecosystem which is subject to temperate climate conditions.' The tooltip also shows a link to the ontology entry.

Ontologies can also be used when referring to publications and personnel. For publications Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) and PubMed identification numbers (PMID) can be used, and ORCIDs (Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier) can be used for registered people. These can be selected similarly as described above for the envO ontology. By inputting values (as the listed examples below) will provide links for attributes like *original publication* and *Collector ORCID*. Links will lead to the DOI target, PubMed page or ORCID page.

- DOI example
 - 10.1002/ece3.5991
- PubMed example
 - 32184981
- ORCID example
 - 0000-0002-1825-0097

Coordinate fields also has 2 inputs, the Latitude and Longitude. The CBF accepts the easy-to-use Decimal Degrees (DD) format which looks like this example from the Trondheim fjord: 63.511722, 10.485166. The format only consists of numbers. To be valid the Latitude (first number) must be within -90 and 90, and Longitude (second number) must be within -180 and 180. Saved coordinates for isolates will be shown on the map and will get a google map link. Note that the more decimal numbers are used the more accurate the coordinates are. E.g., 63.511722, 10.485166 is more accurate than 63.5, 10.5.

The screenshot shows the 'Sampling coordinates' field in the CBF form. It has two input boxes: the first contains '63.511722' and the second contains '10.485166'. The field is labeled 'N' and 'E' respectively. There are also icons for help, save, and delete.

About

The Earth Biogenome Project Norge (EBP-N)

Values, Added values, Added sub-values, Delete

Add sub-value

Delete

Add value

When editing the add value button is used for making a list. This can be convenient for situations where more than one information item needs to be stored, like listing 2 names. This function can be used for all attributes. On exporting the data as a tsv these values will be separated by a pipe symbol e.g., Ola Normann|Kari Normann.

Collector	Ola Normann	Add value	+	-
	Kari Normann			

Result:

Collector	- Kari Normann
	- Ola Normann

The Add sub-value function is useful for making lists of hierarchical values, like a sampling location where 3 levels (Region, Municipality, Site) can be listed. On exporting the data as tsv these values will be separated by the less/more than symbol: Troms>Tromsø>Kvaløysletta.

The added values and added sub-values can also be combined as shown in the example below. An added value (-) can get added sub-values (>).

Delete button

The delete button is used to clear the input field for any data, but if used on an added value or sub-value it will remove it. Note, clearing the main value will clear all added values and sub-values.

Linking external media

By using the “§” character most values in a field can be linked with an external URL link. In the example below the collection method (a Swab sample) has been linked with a document on the sampling guidelines for molds. The input field can be given a value e.g., “Swab sample” followed by the paragraph character (§) followed by an URL. Any media supported by a URL link can be made.

- [value]§[URL]
- Swab sample§<https://aemtek.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/AEMTEK-Mold-Sampling-Guide.2019.pdf>

Linking records between databases

If you have a species and want to associate it with an isolate there are two approaches. The species database is regarded as the top level, and therefore a record with the species name should be present before an isolate record is added to the Isolate database. However, this is not required, only advised. The same goes for the Specimen, Sequencing and Assembly databases (Fig. 1) and can be linked similarly as exemplified here with Species Isolates.

1 – Create the isolate record from the chosen species in the [Species database](#).

For this example, first make sure you are logged into the [Isolate database!](#) Then in the [Species database](#), choose and click on a species record. Under the tab “Related records” you can manage what records are connected to the current selected species. Click on the “Create linked record” button as indicated by the red arrow in the screenshot below. A new window or tab will pop up in your web browser and show the input fields for a new isolate record. Add the necessary metadata and click the save button. You have now created a new isolate record and linked it with the species you chose. **If not logged into the Isolate database (or the database you are about to create a new record in), you will get an error message! A good practice is to first fill the mandatory fields only before saving.** You might need to reload the table pages to see the new linked record. In the species database it is advised to enter edit mode and add the isolate name for conveniency (see the third illustration below), as it is not automatically carried over in the current CBF version. Linked isolate entries will be listed in the species database table and vice versa in the isolate database (see the last 2 screenshots below).

You are watching a draft version of this record.

Scapania nimbose (000000430) ^{1.0}

Project ▾ Authorization ▾ Taxonomy Related records Record metadata

Related records

① Isolate name(s)	-
① Isolate	-
① Specimen name(s)	-
① Specimen	-
① Sequencing name(s)	-
① Sequencing	-
① Assembly name	-
① Assembly	-

[Close](#)

Unknown

Isolate Time and location Natural history specimen Collector Taxonomy Related records Record metadata

Isolate

① Isolate name	EBPN_AB_0123_01	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Scientific name	Scapania nimbose	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Sampling status	Collected	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Lifestage		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Relationship		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Sex		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Symbiont		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Risk of mixed samples	-	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Environment material	-	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Environment sample name		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① BioSample accession		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Other information		↔ ⊙ 🗑️

[Cancel](#) [Save](#)

You are watching a draft version of this record.

Scapania nimbose (000000430) ^{1.0}

Project ▾ Authorization ▾ Taxonomy Related records Record metadata

Related records

① Isolate name(s)	EBPN_AB_0123_01	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Isolate	000000001	🗑️
① Specimen name(s)		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Specimen		🗑️
① Sequencing name(s)		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Sequencing	-	↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Assembly name		↔ ⊙ 🗑️
① Assembly	-	↔ ⊙ 🗑️

[Cancel](#) [Save](#)

Result: Species database and Isolate database tables after following the steps above

1.0

Showing records 1 to 25 out of 145

Scientific name	Synonym name	Family	Sampling status	Isolate name(s)	Isolate	Specimen name(s)	S
Schizochytrium sp. (000000435)	-	Thraustochytriaceae	-	-	-	-	-
Helvetia nannfeldtii (000000434)	-	Helvellaceae	-	-	-	-	-
Cortinarius mariekristinae (000000433)	-	Cortinariaceae	-	-	-	-	-
Saxifraga adscendens (000000432)	-	Saxifragaceae	-	-	-	-	-
(000000431)	Dasya adela	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scapania nimbosa (000000430)	-	Scapaniaceae	Collected	EBPN_AB_0123_01	000000001	-	-

1.0

Showing records 1 to 1 out of 1

Scientific name	Species	Isolate identifier	Sampling status	Sampling date	Sampling location	Habitat	Spec
Scapania nimbosa	000000430	EBPN_AB_0123_01 (000000001)	Collected	-	-	-	-

2 – Creating an isolate record first and then linking it with its corresponding species.

Enter the [Isolate database](#) and creates an entry from scratch by selecting “New record.” Fill in the mandatory fields and save the record. Now click on the record you just made in the database and enter edit mode. Go to the “Related records” tab and click the “Create linked record” (the chain icon). This brings up an input field associated with the species id number. In this example we are looking up *Scapania nimbosa* in the [Species database](#) and find its id to be “000000430”. Enter the complete number in the field, click OK, and then click Save. The record link is created bidirectionally. In the species database it is advised to enter edit mode and add the isolate name for convenience, as it is not automatically carried over in the current CBF version. Linked isolate entries will be listed in the species database table and vice versa in the isolate database.

You are watching a draft version of this record.

EBPN_XY_0123_02 (000000002) 1.0

Isolate Time and location Natural history specimen Collector Taxonomy Related records Record metadata

Related records

Scientific name	Scapania nimbosa	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>
Species	<input type="button" value="🔗"/>	
Specimen name(s)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>
Specimen	<input type="button" value="🔗"/>	
Sequencing name(s)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>
Assembly name(s)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>

JavaScript from "ebp-nor.sfb.uit.no"

Enter the identifier of the record you want to link to.

You are watching a draft version of this record.

EBPN_XY_0123_02 (000000002) 1.0

Isolate Time and location Natural history specimen Collector Taxonomy Related records Record metadata

Related records

Scientific name	Scapania nimbosa	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>
Species	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> Create link	
Specimen name(s)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>
Specimen	<input type="button" value="🔗"/>	
Sequencing name(s)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>
Assembly name(s)	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="🔗"/> <input type="button" value="🗑️"/>

Note that when you are in edit mode you can link records by their identifier numbers, while not in edit mode enables you to create new linked records directly.

Error messages

If editing or adding data in a database while not logged in, will result in a 400-error. This can happen if you create a new isolate record from the Species database (See option 1 for linking records above) but you are not logged into the Isolate database.

Errors can occur when using the quick search function (2022-06-07). This is currently a reported bug in the CBF which is to be corrected.

Save often! If you have been inactive on the site for a while you might get the error below. A sort of halfway logged-out state. Reload the page in your browser to correct it. Work is ongoing to improve CBF on this issue by moving it to NIRD for greater stability.

